

ANALYZING LONG-TERM TREE COVER LOSS TRENDS IN ROMANIA'S DORNELOR LAND: A GIS MAPPING APPROACH WITH OPEN DATA

GIS ANALYSIS OF TREE COVER LOSS TRENDS IN ROMANIA'S DORNELOR LAND

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Abstract

Deforestation and forest degradation, the conversion of forested areas to non-forest land uses, pose global challenges. Deforestation in Romania's Carpathian Mountains is persistently expanding, primarily driven by the lucrative economic value of exploited coniferous wood. Suceava County stands out as one of the most extensively deforested areas in Romania. This study, utilizing Open Data from the Global Forest Watch portal and GIS, maps tree cover loss in Romania's Dornelor land from 2000 to 2022. Combining mapping and statistical approaches, it provides a 20-year overview of forest changes. Emphasizing the climate impact in carbon-rich areas like the Dornelor land, the study underscores the need for climate-conscious land use planning. The findings, exemplified by the impact of tree cover loss, can guide broader efforts to identify and address dangerous changes in forest cover.

Keywords: GIS mapping; Long-term trends; Tree cover loss; Open Data; Dornelor land

INTRODUCTION

Forests serve as integral components within both economic and ecological frameworks due to their multifaceted contributions. Notably, the principal role of forests lies in providing wood, a paramount renewable resource pivotal to various economic activities. Beyond timber, these ecosystems yield a diverse array of products, including ornamental trees and shrubs, Christmas trees, willow, forest seeds, berries, edible wild mushrooms, medicinal plants, resin, game, fish, and honey. This intricate tapestry of offerings underscores the profound diversity and economic significance of forests, emphasizing their critical function in bolstering sustainability and biodiversity.

Romania is a country where large-scale illegal deforestation has been a large problem in the past and is still subject to national and international investigations (Kuchlmayr et. al, 2023, Lehermayr et al. 2020).

Deforestation is a subject that was studied extensively in scientific literature, with different purposes. Some relevant studies by Romanian authors are presented here:

Pintilii et al. (2016) utilized Global Forest Watch (GFW) data to assess forest fund evolution in Suceava county, pinpointing areas vulnerable to dangers from illegal deforestation. The study, by analyzing spatial and temporal patterns, enhances our understanding of environmental threats posed by illicit logging in the region.

Costea et al. (2012) employed Landsat 8 spectral analysis to identify deforestation in Apuseni Mountains, Romania, providing a high-resolution perspective on land cover changes. Through precise detection techniques, the research contributes crucial insights into the spatial patterns and extent of deforestation in the Apuseni Mountains, aiding in the formulation of targeted conservation strategies.

Cozma et al. (2023) investigated the exposure of Romanian forests to illegal logging, comparing it with other countries and exploring links between deforestation and economic indicators. The study not only identifies challenges specific to Romanian forestry but also offers a comprehensive understanding of the intricate relationships between economic development and environmental conservation on a global scale.

Dascălu et al. (2023) introduce a novel method for deforestation detection using Sentinel-1 C-band backscattering data, employing a logistic function to model temporal backscatter intensity variability. The approach, applied to tropical and temperate forests in Argentina and Romania, identifies deforestation events and determines their dates based on inflection points of logistic curves fitted to backscatter intensity time series.

In our study we aim to identify the changes in tree cover from the Dornelor land in Romania between year 2000 and 2022 using the GFW datasets on tree cover, tree cover gain and tree cover loss. According to Global Forest Watch (2023), from 2001 to 2022, Romania lost 407 thousand hectares of tree cover, equivalent to a 5.1% decrease in tree cover since 2000. This is useful information but a cartographic timeline approach will provide a much clearer perspective on the changes in tree cover.

The Dornelor land, located in the northern sector of the Eastern Carpathians at an altitude of approximately 900 meters, encompasses nine communities consisting of 49 villages. Bounded by the Suhard Massif to the north, the Călimani Mountains to the south, and the Giumalău and Pietrosu Bistriței massifs to the east, this geographical area covers an area of over 600 km², representing 0.25% of the total land area of the country. The study area includes the entire surface of the communities in the Dornelor land, totaling 1597 km².

The central hub is the urban center of Vatra Dornei, all falling under the administrative purview of Suceava County. The altitudinal gradient within the area ranges from 800 meters in the Dorna Depression to 1900 meters in the Călimani Mountains to the south. Hydrographically, the area is characterized by rivers such as Dorna, Dornișoara, Teșna, Neagra, and Coșna basin.

MATERIALS AND RESEARCH METHOD

a. Data and area of interest

The area of interest was determined by the 9 communes in the Dornelor land. According to Mihalca (2015) the Dornelor land contains the Vatra Dornei municipality and nine communes: Cărlibaba, Ciocănești, Coșna, Dorna Arini, Dorna Candrenilor, Iacobeni, Panaci, Poiana Stampei, Șaru Dornei. The study area's location in Romania can be seen in Figure 1.

The evaluation of tree cover loss within the ecological zone spanning from 2001 to 2021 was conducted using data sourced from GFW (<https://www.globalforestwatch.org>) in conjunction with the Global Land Laboratory Analysis and Discovery platform from the University of Maryland (<https://glad.umd.edu/>). This analysis builds upon the initial research by Hansen et al (2013).

The GLAD Lab’s tree cover gain and net change data sets, which are based on tree height information, are useful for understanding how the world’s total forest area –both gain and loss—has fluctuated over the past 21 years. This data can provide insights into national- and global-scale deforestation and restoration targets.

Fig. 1. The Dornelor Land area in Romania

Data source : ANCPI, 2023

b. Datasets used in the analysis

Tree cover loss signifies a decrease in the coverage of tree canopy within a defined area during a specified timeframe. It quantifies the reduction in the overall presence of trees, commonly expressed as a percentage or in absolute terms. The causes of tree cover loss are diverse, encompassing factors such as deforestation, logging, alterations in land use, wildfires, and natural disasters. Nevertheless, as highlighted by Harris et al (2020), the primary contributor to tree cover loss in Europe is forestry, constituting 95% of the overall loss (Fig. 2).

The dataset under consideration draws from Landsat images, boasting a spatial resolution of 30 meters. It encapsulates three main variables pivotal to the scope of this inquiry:

- Treecover for the year 2000 (treecover2000), is a quantification of the canopy cover generated by vegetation surpassing the height threshold of five meters;
- Forest loss, tracks the transition from a forested state to a non-forested state over the expansive timeframe from 2001 to 2021. This variable, highlights the areas undergoing transformations in forest status over the specified period.

- Annual forest loss (lossyear), serves as a crucial indicator of the annual loss of forest cover within the dataset. It is structured such that a value of 0 denotes the absence of forest loss. Conversely, values ranging from 1 to 21 are employed to quantify the year of forest loss, each representing a consecutive year starting from 2001.

Fig. 2. The main drivers of tree cover loss

Source : Harris et al., 2020

c. Tools and processes

The chosen tool for data analysis was the ArcGIS Pro platform. We used ArcGIS Pro, an advanced GIS solution, to analyze changes in tree cover over time in the study region. The data was adjusted to match the location of the Dornelor land.

The GFW dataset, containing information on tree cover loss, was processed and tailored to fit the study area. Using ArcGIS Pro allowed us to thoroughly analyze the patterns and trends in tree cover loss over time. Various geospatial techniques and tools in ArcGIS Pro were used to understand the dynamics and extent of tree cover loss during the designated time period.

The use of GIS and ArcGIS Pro highlights the scientific approach used in the investigation, providing a strong platform for analyzing and visualizing environmental changes. The results

of this spatial analysis give valuable insights into the dynamics of tree cover loss, improving our understanding of ecological changes in the studied region. ArcGIS Pro allows for representing the results as complex and easy to understand maps, tables and charts and do very useful spatial analysis operations easily.

I did further data processing by loading the data into a PostgreSQL database for the purpose of conducting statistical analyses on tree cover loss spanning the years 2000 to 2021.

The data loading process encompassed various pivotal stages (as illustrated in figure 3), each contributing to the seamless integration and analysis of the dataset:

1. Initial Database Setup:

- The inception of the data loading procedure involved the creation of a PostgreSQL database. This step was crucial in creating a well-organized and structured environment, ensuring efficient storage and management of the incoming data.

2. Creating Tables for Tree Cover Loss Data:

- Within the PostgreSQL database framework, I created a dedicated table specifically tailored for tree cover loss data. This table contains essential attributes such as the extent of tree cover loss, the respective years when the loss occurred, and the area associated with each polygon representing tree cover loss.

3. Data Import:

- The subsequent phase involved the conversion and loading of the remaining dataset into the PostgreSQL database. This process entailed the conversion of raster data sourced from Global Forest Watch into polygons. Once completed, a spatial data import operation was conducted, ensuring the accurate representation and preservation of geographical information.

4. Querying and Analysis

- With the dataset successfully integrated into the PostgreSQL database, the analytical capabilities of SQL queries were harnessed. This step facilitated the execution of comprehensive statistical analyses, providing valuable insights into patterns and trends related to tree cover loss.

5. Result tables and charts:

- Leveraging the power of SQL queries, the extracted data from the database was utilized to generate result tables and charts. These visual representations served as effective tools for depicting the evolution of tree cover loss over time. The combination of tables and charts offers a comprehensive and intuitive overview, enabling stakeholders to grasp the dynamics and trends inherent in the dataset.

Concluding the analytical phase, the utilization of the ArcGIS Pro platform played a pivotal role in translating the calculated insights from PostgreSQL into visually informative tree cover loss maps. This integration of spatial data and calculations allowed for a seamless transition from the relational database system to a geospatial context, offering a holistic perspective on the observed patterns.

The advantages of this approach over traditional raster analysis in GIS software are noteworthy. By leveraging PostgreSQL for complex calculations, the analytical depth increased significantly.

The relational database system provided a foundation for managing and querying the data efficiently, optimizing the overall workflow.

Fig. 3. Processing of Global Forest Watch data

RESULTS

In the initial tree cover dataset from the year 2000, I conducted an analysis to ascertain the extent of tree cover within the designated area. This data processing and examination unveiled compelling insights into the landscape dynamics during that particular time frame. The findings, as illustrated in Figure 4, brought to light that in the year 2000, regions characterized by more than 30% tree cover comprised a substantial 73.7% of the entire Dornelor land area.

This percentage corresponds to a very large area of 117.8 thousand hectares of land adorned with a canopy of trees at that specific point in time. The remaining 41.9 thousand hectares, constituting nearly a quarter of the designated area, exhibited alternative land uses, marking the coexistence of diverse ecosystems within the region.

The dense tree canopy covering a significant portion of the Dornelor land area in year 2000 underscores the region's ecological importance and resilience. This comprehensive analysis serves as a valuable baseline for tracking changes in tree cover and land use patterns over time.

The resulting insights play a pivotal role in enhancing our understanding of the interplay between human activities and the natural environment in the Dornelor region starting from this point in time.

Fig. 4. Forest coverage of the Dornelor land area (year 2000)

After applying the process presented in the previous section, I obtained a raster representing the year of tree loss over the study area. The raster gives a clear view of the areas with the largest forest loss, mostly in the center and to the West of the area and the period when this forest was destroyed. The raster can be seen in Fig. 5.

Fig. 5. Tree cover loss over 21 years in the Dornelor land area

We notice that large areas with complete tree loss are few but lots of smaller areas had been impacted by this phenomenon over the last 21 years. Using PostgreSQL and spatial queries we could calculate the loss year over year for the study area. The results can be seen as a chart in fig. 6 and as a table in Table 1.

Fig. 5. Tree cover loss chart

The basin's data reveals a dynamic deforestation pattern with fluctuating rates, notably intensified in year 2007, 2010, and 2012. While yearly deforestation may seem low, total losses from 2001 to 2022 indicates a 22750 hectares reduction, a 19% decrease in tree cover since 2000.

RESULT VALIDATION

For result validation, historical imagery sourced from Google Earth Pro software was used. The integration of spatial technologies with the global internet has given rise to the development of virtual globes, granting universal access to geospatial data (Elvidge and Tuttle, 2008). According to Allen (2008), a virtual globe is defined as "a 3D software model of the Earth (or another planet) that offers user interactivity and the freedom to explore the globe from various perspectives, positions, and with overlays of real or abstract geographic data."

In version 5.0, Google introduced the "Historical Imagery" feature in the Google Earth software, providing users with the capability to view images of a specific region at different points in time and observe the changes that have occurred over the course of history. GE Historical Imagery, in particular, offers images taken at various periods, making it particularly valuable for applications in land use change detection studies (Malarvizhi et al., 2016).

For the purpose of result validation, the tree loss raster images were exported to vector format and subsequently loaded into Google Earth Pro. Subsequently, a subset from various regions within the study area was selected for comparative analysis against historical imagery and the tree loss results. Figure 7 illustrates the outcomes, demonstrating the accuracy of tree loss information particularly for years with available historical imagery. The depicted area, situated at the boundary between Dorna Căndrenilor and Șaru Dornei, exhibits deforestation over several years.

The depicted figure underscores the precision of the tree loss layer, revealing significant deforestation in the area in less than five years. The deforestation between the imagery acquisition date is highlighted in light gray in the larger areas.

Fig. 7. Tree cover loss result validation against historical imagery

Image Source: Google Earth Pro

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the analytical approach employed has proven to be an effective method for detecting tree cover loss over an extended period. Leveraging GIS technology has facilitated remote analysis, eliminating the need for periodic field visits and manual measurements. This not only enhances the efficiency of the study but also underscores the valuable contribution of geospatial tools in comprehensively understanding and monitoring long-term changes in tree cover.

After running all analyses over the basin, we notice that the data reveals a dynamic pattern in deforestation characterized by fluctuations, with certain years witnessing noteworthy increases and others displaying declines. This implies that deforestation rates do not exhibit a consistent upward or downward trajectory over time. Particularly noteworthy, the years 2007, 2010, and 2012 emerge as periods marked by intense deforestation, evidenced by exceptionally elevated values.

While the annual extent of deforestation may not appear significant relative to the overall forested area, aggregating losses from 2001 to 2022 reveals a substantial reduction of 22.8 thousand hectares in tree cover. This equates to a 19% decrease in tree cover since 2000.

The dataset's significant range in magnitudes underscores the substantial variation in the extent of deforestation from year to year, underscoring the imperative of comprehending the underlying causes.

However, merely relying on GIS and spatial analysis is insufficient for discerning the rationales behind these values. A more in-depth investigation in the area is warranted, incorporating additional factors such as governmental policies, economic activities, climate events, and conservation efforts on an annual basis. This calls for a holistic approach that integrates spatial analysis with socio-economic and environmental contextual factors, providing a comprehensive understanding essential for devising effective strategies to mitigate and manage deforestation in the studied basin.

APPENDICES

Table 1. Yearly and total tree cover loss

Year	Tree cover loss	Total tree cover loss
2001	274.463	274.463
2002	891.426	1165.889
2003	280.669	1446.558
2004	172.483	1619.041
2005	854.348	2473.388
2006	466.909	2940.297
2007	5769.110	8709.407
2008	759.301	9468.708
2009	813.792	10282.501
2010	1593.818	11876.319
2011	1063.952	12940.270
2012	3120.727	16060.997
2013	428.957	16489.954
2014	771.987	17261.941
2015	391.957	17653.898
2016	1051.829	18705.727

Year	Tree cover loss	Total tree cover loss
2017	863.381	19569.108
2018	1027.815	20596.923
2019	467.752	21064.675
2020	906.802	21971.477
2021	342.547	22314.024
2022	435.989	22750.013

USE OF AI IN THE SCIENTIFIC WRITING

During the preparation of this paper the author used GPT4 in order to correct grammar and rephrase certain statements. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and takes full responsibility for the content of the publication.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the results of this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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